

Nerve Fibre Layer Thickness in Different Types of Amblyopia: A Comparative Study Evaluation of the Retinal

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Abstract

Aim: The aim of the present study was to test the hypothesis that eyes with amblyopia may have thicker retina, retinal nerve fiber layer thickness (RNFLT) was investigated in patients with different amblyopia.

Material & Methods: This prospective study was conducted on consecutive patients diagnosed with amblyopia seen at Department of Ophthalmology, SKMCH, Muzaffarpur, Bihar, India in between duration of One year. The study protocol and the methods adhered to the tenets of the declaration of Helsinki for the use of human subjects in biomedical research

Results: Thirty-eight eyes (38 patients) with anisometropic amblyopia, 25 eyes (25 patients) with strabismic amblyopia, 40 eyes (40 patients) with mixed amblyopia, and 10 eyes (10 patients) with anisometropia without amblyopia were included. Thirty-eight eyes (38 patients) with anisometropic amblyopia, 25 eyes (25 patients) with strabismic amblyopia, 40 eyes (40 patients) with mixed amblyopia, and 10 eyes (10 patients) with anisometropia without amblyopia fulfilled study criteria and were included for the study. Average RNFL thickness in anisometropic amblyopia and strabismic amblyopia was similar, and the difference was statistically insignificant compared with the fellow normal eyes ($P = 0.5$ and 0.6 , respectively). All RNFL parameters in amblyopia groups were not statistically significantly different from the normal group. The difference between all the peripapillary parameters in strabismic amblyopia, anisometropic amblyopia, and mixed amblyopia compared with the normal group was not statistically significant. Differences between all the macular parameters with OCT in strabismic amblyopia, anisometropic amblyopia, and mixed amblyopia compared with the normal group were not statistically significant.

Conclusion: Our study showed that RNFL thickness was similar in amblyopic and non-amblyopic eyes between all three amblyopia groups.

Keywords: Anisometropic amblyopia, optical coherence tomography, Retinal nerve fiber thickness (RNFLT), strabismic amblyopia.

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Introduction

Amblyopia is thought to be a developmental condition of spatial vision that is connected with the existence of strabismus, anisometropia, or form deficiency early in childhood. [1] Amblyopia is defined as a unilateral or bilateral reduction in best-corrected visual acuity (BCVA) not attributed to anatomical or pathological ocular abnormalities of the eyes and visual pathways. It affects between 2% and 4% of the overall population. [2] The amblyopic process may affect several stages of the visual system. Shrinkage of cells in the lateral geniculate nucleus that receive input from the amblyopic eye [3,4] and a shift in the dominance pattern in the visual cortex. It is diminished best-corrected visual acuity in one or both eyes caused

by aberrant visual experience during visual development. Causes include strabismus, image blur from refractive error, form deprivation, or a combination of these causes. A role for optic nerve abnormalities, dubbed “dysversion” or hypoplasia, in the origin of vision loss described as amblyopia has been hypothesized by Lempert, who observed this optic nerve abnormality was evident in optic nerve pictures in 45% of 205 amblyopic eyes. [5,6]

However, the effect of an amblyopic stimulus on the retinal ganglion cells is considerably less well-reported, and few investigations reveal inconsistent findings. Various publications observed no change in the thickness of the retinal

nerve fiber layer (RNFL) between amblyopic and healthy eyes. [7,8] In contrast, Yen et al. and Yoon et al. reported a substantial difference in RNFL thickness in eyes with anisometropic amblyopia compared with normal eyes. [9,10] With the emergence of imaging techniques like the scanning laser polarimetry and Optical coherence Tomography (OCT), it has been able to objectively estimate the peripapillary RNFLT (retinal nerve fiber layer thickness) and macular thickness. Optical coherence tomography (OCT) of the peripapillary optic nerve is a non-invasive examination in which the thickness of the retinal nerve fiber layer (RNFL) is assessed. RNFL thickness corresponds with disc area in children. [11] OCT has been used to compare the RNFL of amblyopic and fellow eyes of individuals of varying ages. [12,13] The Stratus OCT3 (Carl Zeiss Meditec, Dublin, USA) produces high-resolution pictures of the RNFL in vitro, equal to 10 μ m histological slices of the retina. The GDx VCC (software version 5.5; Carl Zeiss, San Diego, USA) is a modified scanning laser polarimeter with variable corneal compensation that accounts for corneal birefringence. [14]

Hence, to test the hypothesis that eyes with amblyopia may have thicker retina, retinal nerve fiber layer thickness (RNFLT) was investigated in patients with different amblyopia.

Material & Methods

This prospective comparative study was conducted on consecutive patients diagnosed with amblyopia seen at Department of Ophthalmology, SKMCH, Muzaffarpur, Bihar, India in between duration of One year. The study protocol and the methods adhered to the tenets of the declaration of Helsinki for the use of human subjects in biomedical research

Inclusion Criteria Were:

- BCVA \geq 20/20 in the better eye,
- Age between 5 years and 35 years,
- Intraocular pressure (IOP) $<$ 22 mmHg in both eyes,
- Clear ocular media,
- Normal fundus examination, and unilateral amblyopia due to strabismus, anisometropia, or both.
- Patients with anisometropic amblyopia, strabismic amblyopia, mixed amblyopia, and anisometropia without amblyopia.

Exclusion Criteria:

- Subjects with recent intraocular surgery within 6 months
- Bilateral (emmetropic) amblyopia, deprivation amblyopia, coexisting nystagmus, and any

other coexisting macular or retinal pathology that could affect final BCVA.

- Patients with pathologies that could affect the RNFL measurement (like cataract, retinal/macular pathology, glaucoma, abnormal discs/tilted discs, presence of systemic diseases, or neurological disorders producing RNFL damage), and in whom OCT images had a quality score $<$ 8 (or signal to noise ratio, SNR $<$ 33) or GDx VCC images with score $<$ 8, and GDx VCC images with atypical birefringence pattern (ABP).
- Patients unwilling to participate in the study.

All patients underwent a complete ophthalmic examination, including BCVA testing (Log MAR chart), cover test, ocular motility evaluation, measurement of ocular deviation using the prism bar, slit lamp examination, applanation tonometry, optic disc, and RNFL examination with a 60D/78D/90D lens, fundus examination with indirect ophthalmoscopy, axial length measurement with A-scan, keratometry, peripapillary RNFL measurement with GDx VCC and OCT Stratus 3. All tests to rule out strabismus were done. Intraocular pressure was measured using noncontact tonometry wherever possible. Fundus examination was done using indirect ophthalmoscope and 20D condensing lens. Cycloplegic refraction using appropriate drug according to age was carried out in all children. Other visual function tests like color vision (Ishihara pseudo isochromatic plates), contrast sensitivity (Pelli–Robson contrast sensitivity chart), visual fields (Humphrey’s field analysis/confrontation test/Amsler’s chart), and electrophysiology tests were recorded wherever it was required and possible. Detailed ophthalmological examination both anterior and posterior segment was carried out in all children. OCT examinations were performed using a spectral domain optical coherence tomography (SD OCT) device (Topcon 3D Maestro 2000 series, Tokyo, Japan) by the same operator through dilated pupils of at least 5 mm in diameter. “Fast RNFL map protocol” consisting of three circular scans with diameters of 3.4 mm centered on the optic disc was performed along with the “Macular Thickness Map” protocol consisting of six radial scan lines centered on the fovea, each having a 6 mm transverse length. In order to obtain the best image quality, focusing and optimization settings were controlled and scans were accepted only if the signal strength (SS) was $>$ 6 (preferably 9–10). Scans with foveal decentration [i.e. with center point thickness standard deviation (SD) $>$ 10%] were repeated. MT was measured using caliper tool 350 μ m nasally from the fovea between internal limiting membrane and retinal pigment epithelium. FT was measured at the center of fovea using

calliper tool between internal limiting membrane and retinal pigment epithelium. In RNFLT measurement, total RNFLT thickness was taken in the study. All findings were recorded for both the groups Average of right eye (RE) and left eye (LE) values were taken for all the parameters in group 2. One month after first visit (post spectacle wear), amblyopic children (group 1) were asked to patch the normal fellow eye for 4 hours per day and perform near such as reading, writing, drawing, mobile games, and activities computer work. Parents were insisted upon maintaining a diary regarding the same to check for compliance. Group 1 children were followed up with BCVA, MT, FT, and RNFLT at 3, 6, 9, and 12 months along with patch diary for children's compliance.

Statistical methods:

Descriptive analysis was carried out by mean and standard deviation for quantitative variables, frequency, and proportion for categorical variables. Initially, the outcome parameters were compared between amblyopic and normal subjects by using independent sample t-test. The mean values of all the outcome variables within amblyopic subjects were compared between the amblyopic and non-amblyopic eye at each follow-up interval separately using paired t-test. The change in the outcome parameters over the follow-up period within the amblyopic eye was compared by one-way repeated measure analysis of variance (ANOVA). Software IBM SPSS Statistics for Windows, Version 22.0. (IBM Corp Armonk, NY; 2013) was used for statistical analysis.

Results

Table 1: Demographic features of patients in all study groups

	Anisometropic amblyopia Mean (SD), n=38				Strabismic amblyopia (SD), n=25		Mixed amblyopia (SD), n=40		Anisometropia without amblyopia (SD), n=10	
	HA	N	MA	N	MA	N	MA	N	AA	N
Numbers	28	28	10	10	25	25	40	40	10	10
Age (years)	16.4 (7.3)		14.6 (6.4)		14.4 (6.2)		16.2 (7.3)		14.2 (7.2)	
Male: Female	22:6		5:5		17:8		32:8		3:7	
Refractive error (diopter, D)	4.86 (2.75)	1.72 (1.25)	-4.28 (3.5)	-1.38 (1.5)	1.78 (3.60)	1.65 (3.56)	1.05 (5.54)	0.75 (3.32)	-3.84 (2.90)	-1.96 (2.61)
Axial Length (mm)	22.28 (1.05)	22.48 (1.01)	24.86 (1.97)	23.77 (2.25)	23.27 (0.94)	23.17 (1.32)	23.87 (2.11)	23.67 (1.76)	24.06 (2.05)	23.17 (1.96)

Thirty-eight eyes (38 patients) with anisometropic amblyopia, 25 eyes (25 patients) with strabismic amblyopia, 40 eyes (40 patients) with mixed amblyopia, and 10 eyes (10 patients) with anisometropia without amblyopia were included. Thirty-eight eyes (38 patients) with anisometropic amblyopia, 25 eyes (25 patients) with strabismic amblyopia, 40 eyes (40 patients) with mixed amblyopia, and 10 eyes (10 patients) with anisometropia without amblyopia fulfilled study criteria and were included for the study.

Differences between all the macular parameters with OCT in strabismic amblyopia, anisometropic amblyopia, and mixed amblyopia compared with the normal group were not statistically significant.

Discussion

A role for optic nerve abnormalities, termed "dysversion" or hypoplasia, in the genesis of visual loss diagnosed as amblyopia has been postulated by

Lempert, who reported this optic nerve abnormality was present in optic nerve photographs in 45% of 205 amblyopic eyes. [15,16] More recently Lempert has reported reduced optic disc rim areas for both amblyopic and fellow eyes with the reduction most prominent in the amblyopic eyes. [17] Optical coherence tomography (OCT) of the peripapillary optic nerve is a non-invasive test in which the thickness of the retinal nerve fiber layer (RNFL) is measured. RNFL thickness correlates with disc area in children. [18] OCT has been used to compare the RNFL of amblyopic and fellow eyes of patients of varied ages. [21,22] One study found a small statistically significant difference between eyes for anisometropic amblyopia (amblyopic eyes thicker) and no difference for strabismic amblyopia. [19] Another study found no difference but had insufficient numbers to evaluate subgroups by cause. [20]

Table 2: Comparison of retinal nerve fiber layer thickness using Optical coherence tomography (TD-OCT, OCT 3) parameters in different groups as compared with the normal fellow eye

Parameter	Anisometropic amblyopia (SD)	Normal (SD)	P	Mixed amblyopia (SD)	Normal (SD)	P	Strabismic amblyopia (SD)	normal (SD)	P	Anisometropia without amblyopia (SD)
Superior Avg	125.35 (22.36)	127.73 (17.63)	0.22	120.18 (26.74)	127 (18.06)	0.04	112.38 (23.27)	120.80 (28.38)	0.1	124.86 (22.01)
Inferior Avg	117.023 (24.02)	123.63 (22.72)	0.10	118.22 (24.22)	115.75 (20.37)	0.64	118.32 (29.19)	114.26 (21.3)	0.4	112.28 (20.03)
Temporal Avg	73.37 (27.36)	64.30 (12.84)	0.05	75.85 (25.4)	66.04 (13.79)	0.02	64.36 (16.23)	70.42 (18.8)	0.12	63.57 (15.21)
Nasal Avg	80.08 (31.62)	85.25 (21.10)	0.32	80.64 (25.75)	80.40 (23.79)	0.92	80.40 (26.53)	76.10 (23.43)	0.60	72.70 (25.49)
Avg Thickness	96.24 (16.27)	98.32 (12.8)	0.5	96.44 (15.12)	94.16 (19.91)	0.82	93.11 (14.95)	96.24 (17.56)	0.60	(14.55)

Average RNFL thickness in anisometropic amblyopia and strabismic amblyopia was similar, and the difference was statistically insignificant compared with the fellow normal eyes ($P = 0.5$ and 0.6 , respectively). All RNFL parameters in amblyopia groups were not statistically significantly different from the normal group.

Table 3: Comparison of GDx VCC parameters in different study groups as compared with the normal fellow eye

Parameter	Anisometropic amblyopia (SD)	Normal (SD)	P	Mixed amblyopia (SD)	Normal (SD)	P	Strabismic amblyopia (SD)	normal (SD)	P	Anisometropia without amblyopia (SD)
NFI	22.27 (13.65)	18.38 (8.82)	0.13	25.5 (15.35)	26.54 (14.94)	0.4	22.38 (16.43)	24.26 (14.12)	0.7	23.67 (9.03)
TSNIT Avg	62.2 (26.16)	56.74 (5.39)	0.22	52.38 (7.13)	52.78 (7.9)	0.70	58.22 (15.93)	58.22 (9.13)	0.1	52.08 (4.28)
Sup Avg	69.31 (24.64)	68.72 (8.69)	0.82	62.64 (9.94)	61.49 (10.17)	0.54	68.22 (17.86)	65.5 (11.06)	0.3	60.96 (6.61)
Inf Avg	68.71 (24.83)	66.25 (9.65)	0.55	61.3 (7.81)	63.12 (8.61)	0.36	64.23 (15.14)	61.78 (9.43)	0.4	58.62 (6.64)
TSNIT Std	22.78 (7.35)	25.40 (5.8)	0.010	22.74 (4.44)	24.36 (3.77)	0.12	22.95 (5.99)	23.37 (4.57)	0.7	19.74 (5.42)

The difference between all the peripapillary parameters in strabismic amblyopia, anisometropic amblyopia, and mixed amblyopia compared with the normal group was not statistically significant.

Table 4: Comparison of Macular parameters with Stratus 3OCT in different Amblyopia groups to Normal

Parameter	Anisometropic amblyopia (SD)	Normal (SD)	P	Mixed amblyopia (SD)	Normal (SD)	P	Strabismic amblyopia (SD)	normal (SD)	P	Anisometropia without amblyopia (SD)
Foveal Thickness	152.82 (26.78)	150.42 (23.84)	0.32	155.86 (32.99)	153.27 (27.65)	0.75	166.1 (36.85)	155.47 (29.94)	0.02	140.33 (22.26)
Total Macular vol	6.31 (0.55)	6.42 (0.38)	0.27	6.47 (0.49)	6.33 (0.5)	0.12	6.38 (0.43)	6.35 (0.42)	0.54	6.05 (0.42)
Outer Sup Avg Vol	1.18 (0.12)	1.23 (0.1)	0.05	1.21 (0.08)	1.19 (0.08)	0.05	1.19 (0.08)	1.19 (0.08)	0.7	1.14 (0.09)
Outer Inf Avg Vol	1.11 (0.13)	1.12 (0.07)	0.42	1.15 (0.1)	1.12 (0.11)	0.07	1.13 (0.09)	1.12 (0.09)	0.55	1.08 (0.08)
Outer Temporal Avg vol	1.1 (0.08)	1.1 (0.06)	0.50	1.12 (0.09)	1.09 (0.1)	0.10	1.09 (0.08)	1.09 (0.09)	0.52	1.02 (0.1)
Outer Nasal Avg Vol	1.27 (0.12)	1.28 (0.08)	0.50	1.29 (0.14)	1.28 (0.13)	0.08	1.28 (0.11)	1.27 (0.09)	0.36	1.21 (0.08)
Inner Sup Avg Vol	0.38 (0.04)	0.39 (0.03)	0.2	0.39 (0.03)	0.38 (0.03)	0.02	0.38 (0.03)	0.38 (0.03)	0.80	0.37 (0.02)
Inner Inf Avg Vol	0.38 (0.04)	0.39 (0.03)	0.20	0.4 (0.03)	0.39 (0.03)	0.10	0.40 (0.03)	0.39 (0.03)	0.80	0.37 (0.03)
Inner Temporal Avg vol	0.36 (0.04)	0.37 (0.03)	0.2	0.37 (0.03)	0.37 (0.03)	0.02	0.37 (0.03)	0.37 (0.03)	0.52	0.35 (0.02)
Inner Nasal Avg Vol	0.38 (0.05)	0.39 (0.03)	0.40	0.39 (0.04)	0.39 (0.03)	0.06	0.38 (0.03)	0.39 (0.03)	0.7	0.37 (0.02)
Central Foveal Vol	0.14 (0.02)	0.14 (0.02)	1	0.14 (0.02)	0.14 (0.03)	0.04	0.15 (0.02)	0.14 (0.02)	0.06	0.13 (0.02)

Differences between all the macular parameters with OCT in strabismic amblyopia, anisometropic amblyopia, and mixed amblyopia compared with the normal group were not statistically significant.

Discussion

A role for optic nerve abnormalities, termed “dysversion” or hypoplasia, in the genesis of visual loss diagnosed as amblyopia has been postulated by Lempert, who reported this optic nerve abnormality

was present in optic nerve photographs in 45% of 205 amblyopic eyes. [15,16] More recently Lempert has reported reduced optic disc rim areas for both amblyopic and fellow eyes with the reduction most prominent in the amblyopic eyes. [17] Optical coherence tomography (OCT) of the peripapillary optic nerve is a non-invasive test in which the thickness of the retinal nerve fiber layer (RNFL) is measured. RNFL thickness correlates with disc area in children. [18] OCT has been used

to compare the RNFL of amblyopic and fellow eyes of patients of varied ages. [21,22] One study found a small statistically significant difference between eyes for anisometropic amblyopia (amblyopic eyes thicker) and no difference for strabismic amblyopia. [19] Another study found no difference but had insufficient numbers to evaluate subgroups by cause. [20]

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Using SD-OCT, Chen et al [24] compared the macular and RNFL thickness in children with anisometropic amblyopia. They reported that the average thickness of the outer macular ring and RNFL were significantly thicker in eyes with anisometropic amblyopia than those with emmetropia. However, following adjustment for axial length and refractive error, this difference was not significant. Furthermore, the macular parameters were not different between treated and untreated amblyopic eyes in their group. They concluded that macular and RNFL thicknesses appear to be more extensively associated with

differences in axial length and refraction than with amblyopic development. Kasem et al [25] investigated the changes in macular parameters (thickness, volume) and peripapillary retinal nerve fiber layer (RNFL) thickness (RNFLT) in different cases of amblyopia versus the healthy fellow eyes using OCT. There were significant differences in mean CMT, mean average macular thickness, mean macular volume, and the mean global RNFLT in the amblyopic eyes versus the fellow eyes. Age and axial length were the only independent variables that statistically significantly correlated with the CMT. They concluded that unilateral amblyopic eyes were prone to have a higher CMT and thicker global RNFL than those of the healthy fellow eyes. However, we could not find any significant difference in the amblyopia group.

Conclusion

Increases in MT and FT in amblyopic eyes, relative to those in normal fellow eyes and the eyes of normally developing children, reduced when BCVA improved following occlusion treatment. There was no difference in RNFLT between amblyopic eyes and normal fellow eyes and normal eyes of normal children before and after occlusion therapy. We advise that more large-scale research addressing the study's shortcomings are necessary to confirm its findings.

References

1. Von Noorden GK. Classification of amblyopia. *American journal of ophthalmology*. 1967 Feb 1;63(2):238-44.
2. Day S. Normal and abnormal visual development. In: Taylor D, Editor, *Pediatric Ophthalmology*. London: Blackwell Scientific Publications; 1990. p. 7-20.
3. Wiesel TN, Hubel DH. Effects of visual deprivation on morphology and physiology of cells in the cat's lateral geniculate body. *Journal of neurophysiology*. 1963 Nov 1;26(6): 978-93.
4. Headon MP, Powell TP. Cellular changes in the lateral geniculate nucleus of infant monkeys after suture of the eyelids. *Journal of anatomy*. 1973 Oct;116(Pt 1):135.
5. Lempert P, Porter L. Dysversion of the optic disc and axial length measurements in a presumed amblyopic population. *Journal of American Association for Pediatric Ophthalmology and Strabismus*. 1998 Aug 1;2(4):207-13.
6. Lempert P. Optic nerve hypoplasia and small eyes in presumed amblyopia. *Journal of American Association for Pediatric Ophthalmology and Strabismus*. 2000 Oct 1;4(5):258-66.
7. Irkeç M, Orhan M, Karaagaoglu E, Bozkurt B. Thickness of the retinal nerve fiber layer in

- patients with anisometropic and strabismic amblyopia. *Strabismus*. 2003 Jan 1;11 (1):1-7.
8. Yen MY, Cheng CY, Wang AG. Retinal nerve fiber layer thickness in unilateral amblyopia. *Investigative ophthalmology & visual science*. 2004 Jul 1;45(7):2224-30.
 9. Yoon SW, Park WH, Baek SH, Kong SM. Thicknesses of macular retinal layer and peripapillary retinal nerve fiber layer in patients with hyperopic anisometropic amblyopia. *Korean Journal of Ophthalmology*. 2005 Mar 1;19(1):62-7.
 10. Sahin G, Dal D. Analysis of retinal nerve fiber layer thickness in anisometropic amblyopia via optic coherence tomography. *Graefe's Archive for Clinical and Experimental Ophthalmology*. 2019 Oct; 257:2103-10.
 11. Huynh SC, Wang XY, Rochtchina E, Crowston JG, Mitchell P. Distribution of optic disc parameters measured by OCT: findings from a population-based study of 6-year-old Australian children. *Investigative ophthalmology & visual science*. 2006 Aug 1;47(8): 32 76-85.
 12. Yen MY, Cheng CY, Wang AG. Retinal nerve fiber layer thickness in unilateral amblyopia. *Investigative ophthalmology & visual science*. 2004 Jul 1;45(7):2224-30.
 13. Repka MX, Goldenberg-Cohen N, Edwards AR. Retinal nerve fiber layer thickness in amblyopic eyes. *American journal of ophthalmology*. 2006 Aug 1;142(2):247-51.
 14. Zhou Q, Weinreb RN. Individualized compensation of anterior segment birefringence during scanning laser polarimetry. *Investigative ophthalmology & visual science*. 2002 Jul 1;43(7):2221-8.
 15. Lempert P, Porter L. Dysversion of the optic disc and axial length measurements in a presumed amblyopic population. *Journal of American Association for Pediatric Ophthalmology and Strabismus*. 1998 Aug 1;2(4):207-13.
 16. Lempert P. Optic nerve hypoplasia and small eyes in presumed amblyopia. *Journal of American Association for Pediatric Ophthalmology and Strabismus*. 2000 Oct 1;4(5):258-66.
 17. Lempert P. Retinal area and optic disc rim area in amblyopic, fellow, and normal hyperopic eyes: a hypothesis for decreased acuity in amblyopia. *Ophthalmology*. 2008 Dec 1;115(12): 2259-61.
 18. Huynh SC, Wang XY, Rochtchina E, Crowston JG, Mitchell P. Distribution of optic disc parameters measured by OCT: findings from a population-based study of 6-year-old Australian children. *Investigative ophthalmology & visual science*. 2006 Aug 1;47(8): 3276-85.
 19. Yen MY, Cheng CY, Wang AG. Retinal nerve fiber layer thickness in unilateral amblyopia. *Investigative ophthalmology & visual science*. 2004 Jul 1;45(7):2224-30.
 20. Repka MX, Goldenberg-Cohen N, Edwards AR. Retinal nerve fiber layer thickness in amblyopic eyes. *American journal of ophthalmology*. 2006 Aug 1;142(2):247-51.
 21. Yen MY, Cheng CY, Wang AG. Retinal nerve fiber layer thickness in unilateral amblyopia. *Investigative ophthalmology & visual science*. 2004 Jul 1;45(7):2224-30.
 22. Colen TP, de Faber JT, Lemij HG. Retinal nerve fiber layer thickness in human strabismic amblyopia. *Binocular Vision and Strabismus Quarterly*. 2000 Jan 1;15(2):141-7.
 23. Irkeç M, Orhan M, Karaagaoglu E, Bozkurt B. Thickness of the retinal nerve fiber layer in patients with anisometropic and strabismic amblyopia. *Strabismus*. 2003 Jan 1;11 (1):1-7.
 24. Chen W, Chen J, Huang J, Xu J, Zhang F, Lu F. Comparison of macular and retinal nerve fiber layer thickness in untreated and treated binocular amblyopia. *Current eye research*. 2013 Dec 1;38(12):1248-54.
 25. Kasem MA, Badawi AE. Changes in macular parameters in different types of amblyopia: optical coherence tomography study. *Clinical Ophthalmology*. 2017 Aug 4:1407-16.